

Follow the Tactile Metronome: Vibrotactile Stimulation for Tempo Synchronization in Music Performance

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a pilot study evaluating the effectiveness of a tactile metronome for music performance and training. Four guitar players were asked to synchronize to a metronome click-track delivered either aurally or via a vibrotactile stimulus. We recorded their performance at different tempi (60 and 120 BPM) and compared the results across modalities. Our results indicate that a tactile metronome can reliably cue participants to follow the target tempo. Such a device could hence be used in musical practice and performances as a reliable alternative to traditional auditory click-tracks, generally considered annoying and distracting by performers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Much research has so far been devoted to the study of the psycho-physical properties of the sense of touch [1]–[4] and to the development of new, tactile-enabled interfaces capable of addressing this rich sensory channel. In recent years, research in this field has been fostered by the ongoing “mobile revolution” and the widespread availability of actuators for mobile and wearable devices [5].

Increasing interest has also been dedicated to the role of haptic feedback and stimulation in the context of musical interaction [6]–[9]. Haptic perception plays an important part in the process of embodiment of a musical instrument, in shaping the perceived qualities of an acoustic musical instrument [10] and, in expert performance, for tasks such as articulation and timing [11]. Guitarists, for instance, have stated to rely on tactile cues for timing tasks [1].

At the same time, several patents for tactile metronomes [12], [13] have been filed in the last decade, and commercial tactile-augmented devices have started to appear on the market [14], [15], claiming to be able to provide musicians with reliable tempo cues. Surprisingly though, no quantitative evaluation of the capability of the sense of touch to process such information, in the context of music performance, has been conducted so far [16]. Most of the litera-

ture in the field of synchronization studies to a metronome signal is mostly limited to tapping experiments [17], in which participants are not actively engaged in any activity. The results from these experiments, while still extremely valuable to evaluate the performance of tactile perception in synchronization tasks, cannot be directly applied to the context of music performance.

The development of the aforementioned commercial products, although not supported by perceptual evidence, testifies nonetheless the interest of researchers, industry and general public for haptic-enabled interfaces targeted to musicians.

With this study, we aimed at performing a pilot, quantitative evaluation, by providing evidence that vibrotactile stimulation can proficiently be used to convey tempo information in music performance. We designed a synchronization tasks in which participants are actively engaged in musical task, such as performing an ascending and descending scale on a classical guitar.

Ultimately, our goal is to provide evidence that haptic technology can be extremely beneficial for musical training and rehearsal: by delivering musical information through haptic cues, auditory cognitive load can be reduced, allowing musicians to redirect their auditory attention to other tasks.

2. PREVIOUS WORK

Few researchers have investigated the use of tactile stimulation in the context of musical interaction. Several works, for instance, have addressed the evaluation of rhythm perception through the sense of touch [18], [19], by showing that tactile rhythm discrimination performs comparatively well compared to audition.

Michailidis and Berweck [20] developed a *tactile feedback tool* to inform musicians about the successful activation of effects using a foot pedal during live performance.

Schumacher et al. [21] investigated the effectiveness of using haptic cues in the context of interaction with a live-electronics environment for composition and performance. By means of two vibrating actuators attached to the back of a performer, the authors conveyed information about the state of the live-electronics system as well as tempo and articulation cues. These cues are traditionally delivered via auditory or visual displays [22], but this practice is often

judged as obtrusive and distracting by performers. Participants in the pilot study expressed positive feedback about the tactile display, especially for what concerns the tempo information, but no evaluation was carried on about the effectiveness of the haptic cues.

3. EVALUATION OF A TACTILE METRONOME

A prototype of a tactile metronome was designed and built using off-the-shelf hardware components. This device was used for conducting a pilot test aimed at characterizing the effectiveness of such a device in music performance.

3.1 System Design

A VPM2 actuator driven by an Arduino Mini-Pro and a ULN2803A¹ motor driver was used to deliver the metronome signal. This inexpensive motor can be driven using a PWM signal which allows only one control parameter: the duty cycle of the PWM wave, ranging from 0 to 1. This can be effectively considered as a control over the intensity of vibration.

The intensity was set to a 0.8 value for the duty-cycle of the PWM wave; this value is well above the perceptual threshold we identified in a previous study [23], which is set at 0.2. The intensity value remained constant throughout the tests and across participants.

The actuator was fixed to the left upper arm of the performer (see Fig. 1). This location was chosen mainly because it did not hinder participants movements, and because sensitivity in this area is reported to be high enough [24] to allow reliable perception of the tactile metronome signal. Other locations were tested: the left wrist was judged by the performers as obtrusive and disturbing; the left ankle caused some of the stimuli to go undetected since some of the non classically trained participants tended to tap along the tempo with their left foot.

Figure 1: On the left, one participant wearing the tactile display on her left arm (circled in red). On the right, one VPM2 actuator.

A software control environment written in Max² was designed to generate synchronized tactile and auditory metronome tracks, and to record musicians' performance. The auditory metronome was delivered through headphones

¹<http://pdf.datasheetcatalog.com/datasheet/SGSThompsonMicroelectronics/mXssxrt.pdf>

²<http://www.cycling74.com>

connected to an external RME Fireface 400³ audio interface. Only the left channel was used to match the lateralization of the tactile stimulus. Headphones were also used to deliver quiet white noise to mask actuator noise during the tactile metronome trials.

The overall latency of the system was also evaluated: a PCB Piezotronics accelerometer⁴ was attached to the actuator. The output from the sensor was connected to one of the external audio interface input channels. The delay of the interface had previously been estimated to be in the order of 2.5 ms looping the output back into the input, and using a Max input-output buffer. Using this setup, the delay between the serial commands sent to the Arduino board and the activation of the motor was evaluated to be in the order of 3 ms. In a previous study [23], we evaluated to 15 ms the time needed for the actuator to reach its supra-threshold amplitude vibration from a steady state. Hence, the system combined (i.e. mechanical and perceptual) total delay was estimated to be around 18 ms. This delay has been taken into account in the analysis of the preliminary data. For the auditory metronome and recording system, the aforementioned audio interface was used. We assumed the delay added by transmission through the headphones and microphone wires to be negligible, thus obtaining an overall delay for the recording apparatus and auditory metronome to be in the order of 2.5ms. These delays have been taken into account in the analysis of the preliminary data.

3.2 Methodology

Four guitar players⁵ were asked to play the first seven notes (ascending and descending) of a G major scale while synchronizing to either a tactile or an auditory metronome. The G major scale is generally recognized as an easy exercise for experienced players and was hence chosen so not to present participants with a too demanding task [25], while still engaging them in an ecologically valid musical task. The tactile stimuli were delivered through our display, while the auditory stimuli were delivered via headphones.

To ensure that neither the auditory nor the tactile metronome stimuli would be perceived as *stronger*, an equalization phase was performed for each participant prior to the beginning of the experiment. Each was presented with both the tactile and the auditory click-tracks and asked to evaluate the *perceived intensity* of the auditory track relatively to the tactile one, which was fixed as reference. Participants instructed the experimenter to increase or decrease the volume of the auditory click-track in order to match the perceived intensity of the two stimuli. Subsequently participants were exposed to four metronome conditions, varying sensory modality and metronome speed (expressed in Beats Per Minute, or BPM) in random order:

- Tactile Metronome at 120 BPM,

³https://booking.cirmmt.org/media/model/71/fface400_e.pdf

⁴<https://booking.cirmmt.org/media/model/420/352C23.pdf>

⁵ Participants reported having at least 3 years of formal or informal practice on the instrument

- Tactile Metronome at 60 BPM,
- Auditory Metronome at 120 BPM,
- Auditory Metronome at 60 BPM

Participants were asked to play synchronously with the metronome track while being recorded through a microphone. They could start their performance at any time after the metronome signal had started, and each recording session lasted 60 seconds (i.e. after they played 120 notes at 120 BPM or 60 notes at 60 BPM). Participants performed each condition only once.

At this preliminary stage we decided to test only two tempi. The 60 and 120 BPM values were chosen since they are generally associated by musicians to, respectively, a slow and a fast tempo [26].

Figure 2: Raw data points showing time interval between each note played by musicians, at both tempi and metronome modalities. The target tempo corresponds to 1000 ms for 60 BPM (in red) and 500 ms for 120 BPM (in blue).

3.3 Data Analysis

The audio files were analyzed to extract onset information from participants’ performances. We tested several onset detection algorithms but none succeeded in accurately analyzing the recorded data. Therefore we manually annotated the onset on the audio files to match the attack of each guitar pluck (see Fig. 3). Interpolation was used to compensate for missing plucks.

These onsets were compared to the metronome signal in order to evaluate participants’ asynchrony in each modality, moreover participants’ deviation from the target tempo was also evaluated.

3.4 Results

An asynchrony vector (representing participants’ *lag* or *delay* with respect to the metronome signal) was computed for each participant by subtracting plucking-time vectors

Figure 3: An excerpt of one performance (60 BPM Tactile). Recorded guitar plucks are shown in blue. The red lines indicate the manually annotated onsets. Time scale is visible on the top (time in seconds).

to metronome-time vectors. The average results across participants are shown in Tab. 1: participants plucks happen after the corresponding metronome signal and this delay is much more pronounced for the tactile modality. This suggests, in accordance with findings reported in the psycho-physical literature [27], that the processing time for the tactile metronome signal is higher than for the auditory one. Fig. 4 illustrates the distribution of the asynchrony data about the median value.

Modality	60 A	60 T	120 A	120 T
Asynchrony (ms)	41.77	77.63	31.73	111.85

Table 1: Average asynchrony times across participants for each modality (A for auditory metronome, T for tactile metronome). Positive values indicate that, on average, the plucking happened **after** the metronome tick.

Fig. 2 illustrates the distribution of the raw data points for each note Inter Onset Interval (IOI) across participants, tempi and sensory modalities. The plot shows that, for both the tactile and auditory conditions, participants play each note with an interval fluctuating around 500 ms or 1000 ms for 120 BPM and 60 BPM respectively. The fluctuations are more pronounced at 60 BPM, consistently for both modalities.

Fig. 5 shows the distribution of the average deviation time from the target tempo participants were supposed to follow. This is expressed as a deviation from IOI. Again, as remarked in fig. 2, participants’ timing is more accurate for the 120 BPM tempo compared to the 60BPM, and their performance is comparable across modalities in this case. This suggests that the tactile metronome can still be used to cue participants to follow the right tempo.

4. DISCUSSION

Results from the asynchrony analysis (Tab. 1 and Fig. 4) give multiple indications:

Asynchrony is generally more pronounced at 60 BPM in the auditory modality, while the mean value indicates an increased value for the 120 BPM for the tactile modality. Participants’ reaction time to the metronome ticks delivered via the tactile display is substantially slower than for

Figure 4: Distribution of the RMS median values illustrating asynchrony with respect to the metronome signal for each modality.

Figure 5: Distribution of the RMS median values for the deviation from the target tempo expressed as an Inter Onset Interval (IOI).

the auditory click-track. Also the response time fluctuates considerably around the median value, suggesting that adaptation and masking effects might influence the perception of the tactile stimuli during each take. This increased delay in reaction time could be due to multiple factors: low intensity of the tactile stimuli; transmission speed through the tactile sensory system. The slower response could also be due to the high motor complexity of our task (playing guitar) which could. Given the small sample size we could not identify a trend in this fluctuations.

The deviation-from-target-IOI analysis (Fig. 2 and 5) indicates that using the tactile click-track, participants are capable of following the target tempo as accurately as with the auditory metronome. For the 1000 ms target (60 BPM), the median deviation value is around 40 ms for both modalities, and the magnitude of fluctuation is comparable. For the 500 ms target (120 BPM), the media is at 22 ms for the auditory modality and 27 ms for the tactile. In both cases the data fluctuates more around the median for this target IOI than the previous one.

Overall these preliminary, descriptive analyses indicate that a tactile metronome can cue performers to follow a given target tempo with an accuracy comparable to that of an auditory click-track. The absolute delay is increased up to an average of 111.85ms for the 120 BPM tactile click-track. This increased reaction time could be compensated for by anticipating the tactile-click track by the necessary amount of time necessary for perception and processing of the tactile stimuli.

4.1 Future Work

Further investigation is needed to more precisely characterize the asynchrony due to increased processing time of the tactile stimuli. Moreover, different body locations should be tested to assess the variation of delay in reaction time in relation to the stimulated body part.

The small sample size allowed us only to perform a descriptive analysis of the data; a larger sample size will be needed for further statistical analysis. These questions will be object of the continuation of this study which will be

performed on 12 expert guitar players.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a pilot experiment conducted on guitar players to assess the effectiveness of a tactile metronome for a music performance and practice. Participants were asked to play synchronously with a click-track, which was delivered either aurally or via a vibrotactile display.

The presented results, while preliminary, show that vibrotactile stimulation can effectively provide musicians with the necessary cues to play at the given tempo. In particular, deviation from target IOI was shown to be comparable between the auditory and the tactile modality. Absolute timing with respect to the metronome track showed higher asynchrony for the tactile click-track; this is most likely due to the increased processing time of a tactile stimuli. This asynchrony, if well characterized in advance, can be accounted for in the design of future tactile metronome interfaces.

Ultimately, we have showed that a tactile metronome can be successfully used to convey tempo information to musicians engaged in a demanding task. Such devices, if routinely integrated in musical practice, could expand performance and rehearsal possibilities.

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